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swarmchestrate

APPLICATION-LEVEL SWARM-BASED ORCHESTRATION ACROSS THE CLOUD-TO-EDGE CONTINUUM

D6.1 Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan

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Abbreviations

Term	Meaning
BG	Background
CA	Consortium Agreement
D	Deliverable
D&C	Dissemination & Communication
DID	Distributed Identifiers
DMS	Document Management System
DoA	Description of Action
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EC	European Commission
FG	Foreground
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IoT	Internet of Things
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
M	Month
R&I	Research & Innovation
SDO	Standards Developing Organisation
SME	Small-Medium Enterprise
SSI	Self-Sovereign Identity
T	Task
TOSCA	Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
ULR	Universal Resource Location
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

The deliverable at hand lays down a comprehensive communication, dissemination and community-building strategy that has been developed to maximise the impact of the Swarmchestrate project. It details the outreach strategy, identifies the target stakeholders, outlines the envisaged dissemination and communication activities, the tools used to execute them, as well as the measurement of their impact. It is aimed as a guidance document for the consortium partners to align on the main objectives and planned communication and dissemination activities, but also to coordinate the close interaction with other R&I projects, including but not limited to those of the DATA-01-04 call.

The main objectives to be met are:

- Establish a distinctive and recognizable brand identity that will support promotional and marketing efforts.
- Achieve broad visibility and raise awareness about Swarmchestrate and its results.
- Reach, stimulate and engage with a critical mass of relevant stakeholders to ensure that the results of the project are effectively showcased, validated and possibly further adopted.
- Support all consortium partners in attracting new stakeholders to the Swarmchestrate ecosystem by creating meaningful communications.
- Foster impactful contribution to standardisation bodies and open source communities, and establish liaisons with relevant projects and initiatives.

Furthermore, the preliminary exploitation intentions of the consortium partners are presented, in a first attempt to lay the path for the exploitation of the project's outcomes and the promotion of innovative solutions based on the Swarmchestrate developed technologies and architectures.

1. Introduction

1.1 Document Purpose

This document has been prepared in the context of WP6 “Establishing Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation” and reports on and highlights the work performed during the first 6 months of the project. It defines the communication, dissemination and community-building strategy, describes the activities Swarmchestrate is (or will be) pursuing to guarantee broad visibility, adequate promotion, and uptake of project results, and presents the preliminary exploitation intentions of the consortium partners.

This document is considered dynamic, includes guidelines and can be edited for updates and adjustments overseen by the D&C Leader at the time of writing. The Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation plan will be periodically evaluated and adjusted throughout the project duration. Major results and updates will be included in the upcoming deliverables on M18 and M36 of the project, as well as in the periodic reports.

1.2 Document Structure

The sections of the deliverable at hand are organised in the following manner:

Section 2 introduces the Swarmchestrate project, its vision and objectives; presents the overarching dissemination and communication objectives and phases; identifies the targeted stakeholder groups; and describes the internal organisation details.

Section 3 elaborates on the project’s visual identity elements.

Section 4 outlines the channels used to reach a broad audience and describes the various types of dissemination tools and activities in more detail.

Section 5 provides the scheduling of the dissemination and communication activities during the project lifetime.

Section 6 gives the details on how the dissemination and communication effort in the project is monitored.

Section 7 lays down the preliminary exploitation considerations of the consortium partners.

Section 8 concludes the document.

2. Dissemination and Communication Strategy

Efficient dissemination and communication activities during the course of the Swarmchestrate project shall ensure its short- and long-term success. Promotion, dissemination, stakeholder engagement and impact creation activities take centre stage in the collective Swarmchestrate effort and will be closely coordinated among the various WPs to create a cohesive plan of actions for the effective engagement of all target stakeholders in the fog computing, edge computing and IoT domains.

Swarmchestrate shall engage in dissemination, communication and community building towards industry, SMEs, standardisation bodies, researchers and open source communities, as well as citizens, policy makers, public authorities and relevant initiatives, as appropriate. To showcase the benefits of the developed Swarmchestrate solutions will be a core mission around which our promotional efforts will be organised, starting from the demonstrators in the context of flood prevention, parking space management, video analytics and a digital twin of natural habitat.

A comprehensive and well-structured set of dissemination activities are aimed to raise awareness and encourage uptake of developed concepts, technologies, use cases, and results. This will include online and offline communications, digital presence, participation in and organisation of events, contributions to standardisation, interactions and liaisons with relevant initiatives and projects.

The ambition behind the dissemination and communication activities of Swarmchestrate translates into the following overarching objectives:

- *Ensure broad visibility and raise awareness about Swarmchestrate, spread knowledge about the project and its results, establish a distinctive and recognizable identity that will support marketing efforts.*
- *Reach, stimulate and engage a critical mass of relevant stakeholders to ensure that the results of the project are effectively showcased, leading to validation, improvement and possibly further adoption of the developed technologies and concepts, especially towards target vertical sectors.*
- *Facilitate exploitation of the project's outcomes and promote the development of innovative solutions based on the Swarmchestrate developed technologies and architectures.*
- *Foster impactful contribution to relevant standardisation bodies and open source communities as appropriate.*
- *Ensure close interaction with sister R&I projects in the DATA-01-04 call.*

2.1 Project Objectives

PROJECT VISION

Collecting and analysing large amounts of data in the Cloud-to-Edge computing continuum raises novel challenges. Processing all this data centrally in cloud data centres is not feasible

anymore, as transferring large amounts of data to the cloud is time-consuming, expensive, degrades performance and may raise security concerns. Therefore, novel distributed computing paradigms, such as edge and fog computing, emerged to support processing data closer to its origin. However, such hyper-distributed systems require fundamentally new methods.

To overcome the limitation of current centralised application management approaches, Swarmchestrator will develop a completely novel decentralised application-level orchestrator, based on the notion of self-organised interdependent Swarms. Application microservices are managed in a dynamic Orchestration Space by decentralised Orchestration Agents, governed by distributed intelligence that provides matchmaking between application requirements and resources, and supports the dynamic self-organisation of Swarms. Knowledge and trust, essential for the operation of the Orchestration Space, will be managed through blockchain-based trusted solutions using methods of Self-Sovereign Identities (SSI) and Distributed Identifiers (DID). End-to-end security of the overall system will be assured by utilising state-of-the-art cryptographic algorithms and privacy-preserving data analytics.

Due to the imminent complexity of the decentralised system, novel simulation approaches will be developed to test and optimise system behaviour (e.g., energy efficiency) in the early stages of development. Additionally, the simulator will be further extended into a digital twin running in parallel to the physical system and improving its behaviour with predictive feedback. The Swarmchestrator concept will be prototyped on four real life demonstrators from the areas of flood prevention, parking space management, video analytics and a digital twin of natural habitat.

PROJECT OBJECTIVES

- *Develop an application-level decentralised orchestration framework (incorporating compute, data and code), utilising Swarm-based distributed intelligence for highly dynamic and distributed Cloud-to-Edge computing infrastructures.*
- *Dynamically create and manage a set of interconnected Swarms by matching application requirements with resources across the distributed Cloud-to-Edge infrastructure.*
- *Develop matchmaking algorithms using decentralised AI methods that will dynamically pair application requirements with resource characteristics, in order to optimise energy efficiency, resilience and effectiveness of the system.*
- *Develop a trusted, reliable, secure and transparent knowledge management infrastructure.*
- *Develop a simulation environment based on the novel decentralised orchestration concept of the project that will be utilised to measure and finetune the effectiveness of the implemented solutions and algorithms. Additionally, further extend this simulator to be used to create a digital twin of the orchestration solution, supporting the live system by recommending predictive modifications of the system setup and its parameters.*

- *Implement four real-life application demonstrators utilising Swarmchestrate services in realistic scenarios where large amounts of data, collected at the network edges, need to be efficiently processed.*

2.2 Target Groups and Messages

The successful realisation of the project goals hinges on the effective communication of our findings, innovations, and best practices to a carefully identified set of targeted user groups. These user groups, each playing a pivotal role in the project's ecosystem, range from those directly involved in application development and IoT devices manufacturing, to policymakers and the general public. For each, we have developed tailored messages designed to resonate, inform, and inspire action. This section delves into the specifics of these stakeholders and the key messages we intend to share, setting the stage for a comprehensive strategy that ensures our project's outcomes are widely understood, accepted, and implemented.

Figure 1 Swarmchestrate Stakeholders

Table 1 outlines the strategic approach to engaging with our stakeholders.

Table 1 Messages per Stakeholder Group

Key Stakeholder	Purpose	Message
Application developers/ owners	End users of the Swarmchestr ate framework. As the main target users of the Swarmchestr ate framework, this group is the primary stakeholder.	A novel decentralised framework is offered that provides new possibilities in the form of more efficient application deployment and run-time management.

Key Stakeholder	Purpose	Message
IoT device manufacturers	Added value when selling hardware devices.	Device manufacturers can utilise the Swarmchestr ate framework to offer a fully managed solution on top of the IoT devices.
Companies developing and offering hyper-distributed data processing applications	Enhanced market competitiveness.	Introducing the elaborated mechanisms will simplify offering open and interoperable systems.
Companies in the public and private sectors using hyper-distributed data processing applications (e.g., manufacturing, traffic and utility service management)	Expanded application portfolio.	Utilising hyper-distributed data processing applications will open the possibility to currently not feasible application scenario(s).
End user companies of Cloud-to-Edge applications in manufacturing, public sector, and beyond	Solutions to large-scale, complex problems.	Our solutions will mitigate current data processing limitations in the Cloud Continuum.
Citizens, general public	Improved quality of life.	Swarmchestr ate will demonstrate the benefit of its solutions in four selected use-cases.
Academia, Research communities, Other research projects, R&I departments of IT companies	Disseminating our findings and outputs. Enabling the utilisation of Swarmchestr ate outputs to further improve science and technology.	Presenting our results throughout academia and research communities so we can collaborate with similar initiatives.
Open source associations, SDOs, Technology Clusters, Policy Makers	Awareness raising.	Our approach can be exploited via decision-making groups, and collaborations can be identified.

2.3 Dissemination and Communication Phases

Swarmchestrate outreach and impact creation strategy and plan includes offline and online communication, digital presence, participation in and organisation of events, interaction with sister R&I projects in the DATA-01-04 call, as well as liaisons with relevant stakeholders and similar Horizon Europe projects coming from previous and future calls.

Swarmchestrate will follow a phased approach to defining, planning, organising and exploiting a rich set of activities and instruments in the most effective way towards building a strong and vibrant community.

Figure 2 Swarmchestrate D&C Phases

Phase 1 - Awareness creation and marketing foundation (M1-M12)

During this current phase, we design the dissemination and communication strategy, define the target user groups, plan dissemination & communication activities and a selection of dedicated communication tools. Moreover, we start to inform all relevant stakeholders about the scope and the objectives of the Swarmchestrate project and to define the liaisons and interaction mechanisms with the rest of the DATA-01-04 call projects.

Outcomes/Measures:

- ✓ The Swarmchestrate website (swarmchestrate.eu) created and launched.
- ✓ Visual guidelines published and are available to all project partners.
- ✓ The communication, dissemination and exploitation plan (deliverable D6.1 at hand).
- ✓ A strategic project presentation (slide deck) created by month 9 (September 2024).
- ✓ Dedicated social media channels set up and animated ([Twitter/X](#) and [LinkedIn](#)).
- ✓ A first project flyer created and the 1st newsletter to be circulated.
- ✓ A first video to be created on the concept to raise awareness by month 12 (December 2024).
- ✓ Creation of the first liaisons and organisation of common events with sister R&I projects in the DATA-01-04 call.

Phase 2 - Community outreach and engagement bootstrap (M13-M24)

During Phase 2 of our dissemination and communication plan, we will actively reach out to the main target stakeholders towards generating interest in Swarmchestrate on-going activities. We will set-up a solid foundation for the planned dissemination and demonstration activities, approaching target stakeholders to provide support for the promotion of the project, most prominently promoting the initial project outcomes, around month 18 of the project. In this

phase, the planning for participation to and organisation of events will strengthen, including webinars and workshops.

Outcomes/Measures:

- ✓ Slide-based presentations of first project results.
- ✓ Continued animation of social media channels.
- ✓ Several blog posts published on the Swarmchestr^{ate} website and social media.
- ✓ Dispatch of quarterly newsletters and targeting appearances to press media.
- ✓ Participation in selected events, to promote the project and its initial results.
- ✓ Organisation and fostering of the first Swarmchestr^{ate}-organised workshop and webinar, as to gather feedback on the initial results of the project by the research and industrial community.

Stage 3 - Global outreach and sustainable impact (M25-M36)

During Phase 3 we will actively engage with and support industry, SMEs and all target stakeholders in the adoption and deployment of the concepts, technologies and tools offered by Swarmchestr^{ate} through dedicated promotional activities. This includes scientific publications, development and distribution of promo materials, deliverables, participation in selected events, organisation of dedicated workshops, demonstrations, training sessions, and liaisons with relevant projects and initiatives. It is expected that standardisation efforts will intensify as the technologies developed will mature along the project's lifetime. Co-organisation of additional workshops and webinars, in collaboration with relevant projects and initiatives

Outcomes/Measures:

- ✓ Promotional materials in various forms.
- ✓ Scientific publications.
- ✓ Established liaisons with relevant projects and co-organisation of workshops and webinars.
- ✓ Press releases, technical reports and deliverables.
- ✓ Additional editions of the newsletter.
- ✓ Dedicated webinars on the released components and training sessions.
- ✓ More videos on the project final outcomes and related to the use case outcomes to promote our work.
- ✓ Contributions to standardisation bodies and open source communities.

2.4 Internal Organisation

The responsibility for managing day-to-day communication efforts, including the maintenance of the project website and updates across social media channels, falls to the D&C Leader who is supported by the designated communication team. This team will also create various communication materials such as brochures, videos, and draft press releases to ensure consistent and engaging messaging.

To streamline this collaborative process, each consortium partner has assigned at least one person as part of the communication team, to actively participate and provide valuable input to enrich the project's communication efforts. The members of the communication team play a crucial role in amplifying the visibility of the Swarmchestrate project, both internally and externally. Their responsibilities extend to assisting in the preparation and dissemination of press releases and leveraging their own networks and communication channels to spread the word about the Swarmchestrate project's initiatives and achievements.

All Swarmchestrate partners are required to document their dissemination and communication efforts consistently by utilising the online Document Management System (DMS) (Nextcloud) within the cloud infrastructure offered by the Project Coordinator, SZTAKI. This systematic approach allows for efficient monitoring of all activities against the established Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). Furthermore, partners are expected to communicate regularly with the project's designated communication team about their dissemination activities. This includes details on presentations delivered, workshops participated in, and any other relevant engagement efforts, ensuring a comprehensive overview of the project's outreach and impact.

2.4.1 Internal Dissemination & Communication Workshop

In order to align all members of the communications team, a dedicated Dissemination & Communication Workshop was delivered in month 4 (April 2024) by the D&C Leader partner Suite5. During this workshop, the following aspects were presented, discussed and clarified:

- the project website;
- the social media accounts;
- the visual guidelines (see Annex A – Swarmchestrate Visual Guidelines);
- the Word & PowerPoint templates;
- the editorial calendar;
- the scientific publications tracking sheet;
- the events radar;
- the KPIs monitoring sheet; and
- other pertinent tools used in our dissemination & communication efforts.

The workshop was recorded and uploaded to the internal project DMS (Nextcloud), so that it remains available for reference, for new members who will on-board the team during the project's duration, etc.

Figure 3 Screenshot from the Internal D&C Workshop

2.5 Funding Acknowledgements

The Swarmchestrate project is co-funded by the European Union’s Horizon Europe Programme [grant number 101135012, budget: €4.3 million], UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government’s Horizon Europe funding guarantee [grant numbers 10101169 and 10102651, budget £938,271], the National Research Foundation of Korea [budget: €214,286] and Seoul National University [budget: €141,943].

Swarmchestrate beneficiaries must acknowledge EU support and display the EU flag (emblem) (Figure 4) and co-funding statement when communicating about the project and disseminating project results. This includes media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as website, brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc., and any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major result funded by the grant.

Figure 4 EU funding logo

Further, when displayed in association with other logos, the emblem must be displayed at least as prominently and visibly as the other logos.

Moreover, it must include the following disclaimer: *“Co-funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them”.*

Information and tips for communicating and raising EU visibility can be found on the pertinent EC website [1].

For collaborative projects which are part of EU-funded consortia, in addition to acknowledging the Horizon Europe funds, the UKRI Horizon Europe Guarantee funding must also be acknowledged. The following applicable sentence must be included: *“This work was funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government’s Horizon Europe funding guarantee [grant number XXX]”*. If there is more than one UK partner involved in the output, then all grant reference numbers from the other UK partners should be included.

More info regarding the acknowledgement of UKRI funding is available at the UKRI Horizon Europe Guarantee guidance [2], query 28.

The whole consortium agreed on following those rules since they are also part of the legal agreements signed in the Grant Agreement. To facilitate this task, different templates have been developed where these requirements have been taken into account.

3. Project Visual Identity

As an EC co-funded project, a clear project visual identity needs to be implemented in order to positively impact the dissemination of respective work and achievements. Visual identity consists of visible assets, such as logo, colour palette, and typography. The recognition and perception of a project is highly influenced by its visual presentation. Effective visual identity is achieved by the consistent use of particular visual elements across all communication channels to create distinction, such as specific fonts, colours, and graphic elements.

The visual identity and sets of guidelines have been finalised since in the first six months of the project in order to secure a strong and unique brand. In the duration of the project, it will be incorporated in all promotional and dissemination materials produced and will be used by all project partners in their communication activities.

The main idea behind the design of the **Swarmchestr^{ate} logo** (Figure 5) is decentralisation as the core pillar of the project, where all nodes are reflected more or less equally, and a central node is absent. A textual part with the name of the project has been added to support the image.

Figure 5 Swarmchestr^{ate} logo

We have further produced a horizontal version of the Swarmchestrate logo, where the image is less prominent compared to the text, but fits better in certain communication media, for example in the website title row.

Figure 6 Swarmchestrate logo horizontal version

Swarmchestrate logo uses the **Croogla 4F** font.

Swarmchestrate project uses the **Overpass** open source, typeface font from Google Fonts [3]. The usage of all versions of this font is allowed. This applies to the website, presentations and all promotional material.

Overpass Bold 12px: ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ

Overpass Italic 12px: abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

Overpass Regular 12px: 1234567890

Swarmchestrate deliverables use the **Calibri Light** font instead, to avoid missing font issues. Calibri Light is standard pre-installed in modern Windows editions, and we anticipate the majority of the deliverable documents to be edited outside design departments. Calibri Light could be used also for presentations in case the Overpass font is missing.

Calibri Light Bold 12px: ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ

Calibri Light Italic 12px: abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

Calibri Light Regular 12px: 1234567890

The colour palette (Figure 7) is based on the logo colour scheme and contains 5 main colours. These are the colours of the various nodes.

Figure 7 Swarmchestrat colour palette

For PowerPoint presentations and Word documents, the colour of standard elements has been defined and locked in the respective templates. To change colours, icons or additional text, editors will find the project colour palette in the templates.

A **PowerPoint presentation template** was created to be used by the partners to create their presentations for all external and internal events, meetings, etc., based on a common look and feel.

Figure 8 Swarmchestrat MS PowerPoint template

A **Word document template** was created to be used by the partners for deliverables (the deliverable at hand follows the defined template).

Figure 9 Swarmchestrate MS Word template

In Annex, the reader can find the visual identity guidelines that have been shared with all the partners internally at the Swarmchestrate consortium; they include the logo, the colour palette and the fonts used. The Swarmchestrate logo is shown in several variations, to be used depending on the background, and in different sizes, to guarantee readability in different sources, e.g. reports, web, presentations. The range of colours to be used in the project are the ones adopted in the logo.

4. Tools and Channels

Swarmchestrate project will employ a multi-faceted approach to engage diverse audiences, including the media, industry stakeholders, and the broader public. Our strategy emphasizes:

1. **Developing a Unified Visual Identity:** Establishing a cohesive visual brand for the project to ensure recognition and consistency across all platforms.
2. **Providing Timely Project Updates:** Sharing the latest project developments and achievements to keep our audience informed.
3. **Broad Dissemination of Findings:** Ensuring the project's results reach a wide audience, emphasising accessibility and comprehension.
4. **Simplifying Complex Information:** Converting technical and scientific findings into easily understandable content, catering to both technical and non-technical audiences.

To effectively convey our message and maximise outreach, we will leverage a combination of primarily digital and secondarily traditional communication mediums. This includes maintaining a dynamic website, actively participating in social media channels, leveraging multimedia materials, and engaging through press and audio-visual media. Our coordinated use of these tools aims to foster awareness and understanding at local, national, and international levels, ensuring that the Swarmchestrate project connects with all pertinent audiences.

4.1 Project Website

The Swarmchestrat project website has been developed in alignment with the communication strategy outlined in the Grant Agreement. It was launched on month 5 of the project (May 2024) at swarmchestrat.eu and swarmchestrat.com domains; a fully functional and responsive website that contains comprehensive information on the Swarmchestrat goals and objectives, with easy access and a friendly interface to retrieve information and any public material generated within the project, as well as materials gathered via the various work packages activities about ongoing projects and relevant initiatives. The Swarmchestrat website will be serving as a cornerstone of our dissemination efforts throughout the project duration, designed to address all target groups associated with the project (see section 2.2).

Figure 10 swarmchestrat.eu Home Page

As shown in Figure 10, the project website’s home page has evolved into a clear and clean communication interface that is easily navigable, containing all relevant project related public information. The site includes the Swarmchestrat logo and long project title, along with the

EU flag, the UKRI logo and the respective acknowledgement messages. and is structured into the following sections:

Figure 11 swarmchestr^{ate}.eu Sitemap

ABOUT

This section contains the information about the project, split in three subsections:

- Project Vision & Objectives: here is an overview of Swarmchestr^{ate} – the project’s scope and main goals are stated in a brief text and broken down into a series of simple, captioned icons, for readability at a glance
- The consortium: presenting and linking all the partners

DEMONSTRATORS

This section gives an overview of the four Swarmchestr^{ate} demonstrators on flood prevention, parking space management, digital twin of natural habitat and a four one which is under consideration at the time of writing this deliverable.

UPDATES

This section covers the latest news and press releases related to the project and will be frequently updated with new articles and relevant project information in order to keep the audience aware of the progress and milestones achieved. At the time of writing this deliverable, the news section gathers a few entries related to the kick-off meeting in Budapest and the presentation of project partners. All updates are also spread through our Twitter/LinkedIn channels to increase their visibility and further resharing. Furthermore, website visitors can subscribe to the newsletter from this section as well (other sections where

visitors can subscribe to the newsletter: the Home Page and the Contact Us page) and will be able to browser previous newsletter issues after their publication.

EVENTS

Future events related to the project such as meetings, workshops or conferences or those that could be interesting due to its relationship with project topic are also gathered under this section. The events are presented in a similar way to latest news.

LIBRARY

The main repository for project outputs, including communication materials, press releases, public deliverables, and more. It is split into six subsections which include:

- Scientific Publications: all the publications related to the project will be gathered here. When available, full paper and/or abstract download link will be provided.
- Presentations: material given at events and workshops will be published here.
- Deliverables: public deliverables which will be uploaded and made available along the project's lifetime will be gathered here.
- Press Releases: material relevant for the media will be published here.
- Videos: a section to collect the videos which will be produced throughout the project's duration (incl. links to the YouTube channel).
- Promo Material: leaflets, brochures, logo and all the material conveying the corporative image of the project will be gathered here.

CONTACT

This page allows website visitors to directly contact the project through a dedicated form, to subscribe to the newsletter, and it also includes links to Swarmchestr^{ate} social media. Messages sent via the contact form are forwarded to info@swarmchestr^{ate}.eu, which is forwarded to the responsible project partners, who will receive the message and respond to it.

At the time of writing, the website has already counted 191 unique visitors, who generated 1.400 page views, as shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12 swarmchestrat.eu Website Analytics

The website provides also information to the visitors on data kept and how they are used in alignment with the GDPR under the Privacy policy link [4] (found in the right of the website footer). It should be noted that all information and e-mails collected are protected under GDPR. Contacts will only be made to those who have submitted their inquiries and newsletters will only be sent out to those who have explicitly requested to receive them. Any person who has subscribed will be allowed to remove their e-mail upon request.

In order to support and amplify the traffic directed to the website, (a) Search Engine Optimisation will progressively increase the number of visits thanks to the implementation of strategies oriented to organic traffic, always considering the keywords identified for it; and (b) Link Building will create synergies between the project's website and the partners' websites as well as with other relevant stakeholders.

For the protection of the website forms, Google Captcha v3 has been put in place. For the management of the use of website cookies, CookieYes has been put in place.

As the main dissemination pillar and by nature a dynamic tool, the website will be continuously updated throughout the lifetime of the project.

4.2 Social Media

As per the communication strategy of the Swarmchestrat project, social media accounts were established as **marketing tools** in order to **promote activities and outputs of the project** on a regular basis, while also **encouraging a wider discussion on the orchestration, IoT and energy efficiency** topics. The platforms selected for this purpose, LinkedIn, X (Twitter) and YouTube, are instrumental in achieving the project's outreach objectives due to their unique audiences

and interaction styles. The communication strategy underlines the project's commitment to leveraging digital channels to maximise impact and encourage active participation from a wide range of stakeholders.

Below, a brief overview of the social media accounts created for Swarmchestrate.

Twitter/X is a very dynamic social network that covers the news in real-time at a global level. Swarmchestrate established its Twitter/X account at the official start of the project (February 2024). At the time of writing this deliverable it counts 69 followers, it has tweeted 13 posts and has been already used to cover the project's kick-off meeting and relevant initiatives and projects' activities. The Twitter/X account will be used for promoting and disseminating the developments inside Swarmchestrate, including news, events, outcomes, etc. Moreover, re-tweets will be made of relevant and interesting content from disparate sources. Last but not least, by following relevant accounts, Swarmchestrate not only gains access to more relevant content and updates, but also acquires more followers.

The credentials for Twitter/X are the following:

- **@swarmchestrate** - Twitter handle, mentions the project **#SwarmchestrateEU** – hashtag

Examples of appropriate hashtags:

- #HEU
- #orchestration
- #swarm
- #EnergyEfficiency
- #edge_computing
- #fog_computing
- #IoT

Figure 13 Swarmchestrat Twitter/X account

LinkedIn is currently the main business network in the world and has more than 150 million users in more than 200 countries and territories. Stakeholders interested in connecting with Swarmchestrat are on LinkedIn, so it is appropriate to implement some actions. A LinkedIn company page for Swarmchestrat was established at the official start of the project (February 2024), to provide a public image on a global scale as a reputable and trustworthy project. It counts, at the time of writing this deliverable, 70 followers and 14 posts have been published. By producing content about the project that our followers engage with and further share with others, our followers become engaged advocates of Swarmchestrat and can expand our global influence. The content generated for LinkedIn will be available in different formats such as project presentations, website blog posts, infographics and videos depending on what updates our content supports and which are the viewing preferences of our target audience. The LinkedIn profile is a supplement to the website, helps driving traffic to it and offers a convenient means to promote the project updates. We will mention partners' LinkedIn pages when appropriate to create positive visit exchanges.

The credentials for LinkedIn are the following:

- [linkedin.com/company/swarmchestrate](https://www.linkedin.com/company/swarmchestrate)

Figure 14 Swarmchestrate LinkedIn account

Table 2 Swarmchestrate Consortium social media accounts

Partner Name	LinkedIn Page	Twitter Handle
SZTAKI	linkedin.com/company/sztaki/	
TUB	linkedin.com/school/tuberlin/	@TUBerlin
ICCS	linkedin.com/company/information-management-unit-imu/	@imu_ntua
TAU	linkedin.com/school/tampere-university/	@TampereUni
UL	linkedin.com/school/university-of-ljubljana/	
IRI	linkedin.com/company/iriul/	@iri_ul
FUELICS	linkedin.com/company/fuelics	
SUITE5	linkedin.com/company/suite5/	@suite5eu

Partner Name	LinkedIn Page	Twitter Handle
FEA	linkedin.com/company/frontendart	@frontendart
FBK	linkedin.com/company/fbkresearch	@FBK_research
UST	linkedin.com/company/ustglobal/	@USTglobal
SNU	linkedin.com/company/seoulnationaluniversity/	@seoulnatluni
ENU	linkedin.com/school/edinburgh-napier-university/	@EdinburghNapier @EdNapierSCEBE
UOW	linkedin.com/school/university-of-westminster/	@UniWestminster

Table 3 Relevant social media accounts

Organisation/ Institution Name	LinkedIn Page	Twitter Handle
EUCloudEdgeIoT	linkedin.com/company/eucloudedgeiot/	@EU_CloudEdgeIoT
EU Science, Research & Innovation	linkedin.com/showcase/european-commission-joint-research-centre/	@HorizonEU
European Commission	linkedin.com/company/european-commission/	@EU_Commission
EU Digital & Tech	linkedin.com/showcase/digital-eu/	@DigitalEU
UKRI- Uk Research and Innovation	linkedin.com/company/uk-research-and-innovation/	@UKRI_News
Artificial Intelligence National Laboratory (MILAB)	linkedin.com/company/artificial-intelligence-national-laboratory-milab/	

YouTube is one of the leading video-sharing platforms at a global level that allows to upload videos and create a community of subscribers. Swarmchestrate will maintain a YouTube channel which will be used to disseminate the Swarmchestrate videos. A YouTube account for Swarmchestrate was established at the official start of the project (February 2024) but has not been used yet.

The credentials for YouTube are the following:

- [ate">youtube.com/@swarmchestrate](https://youtube.com/@swarmchestr<span style=)

4.3 Newsletter

An e-Newsletter will be produced by the Swarmchestrate consortium on a quarterly basis and will play a crucial role in the project's communication strategy, serving as an essential channel for sharing regular updates, project findings and results, news from industrial partners, engaging with stakeholders. These digital bulletins will deliver a curated selection of the project's progress, spotlight upcoming events, and celebrate key milestones and innovations, in an attempt to inform the audience on how they can get in touch with the project.

A registration functionality allowing the interested visitors to subscribe to the newsletter is already available on the Swarmchestrate website; a mailing list is being created, based on subscription, giving the possibility to share the e-Newsletter via mass mailing. Subscribers will receive timely and relevant information straight to their mailbox, helping to keep the all user groups (see section 2.2) well-informed and interconnected.

The first newsletter will be published in July 2024 and subsequently sent out every three months.

The strategy to gain subscribers for the newsletter will include:

1. **Collaborative Content Creation:** Project partners will be invited to contribute articles, insights, or case studies to the newsletter. This collaborative content creation will not only enrich the newsletter's content but also encourage partners to share it within their networks, attracting subscribers interested in diverse perspectives on sustainable agriculture and renewable energy.
2. **Promotion Through Partners' Channels:** Each project partner will be asked to promote the newsletter sign-up link through their existing communication channels. This includes websites, social media platforms, email signatures, and during webinars or workshops.
3. **Promotion of the newsletter on the project webpage** and in social media posts.

Every newsletter issue will be also uploaded to a dedicated section on the project website.

4.4 Promotional Materials

As part of the Swarmchestrate communication strategy, we plan to prepare at least four project brochures and flyers. Technical brochures shall provide information on technical and scientific achievements and the potential project applications, while other presentation material (flyers, posters and roll-up banners) will be used for display in conferences and in exhibition booths.

A Swarmchestrate project flyer will be created by month 7 (July 2024) and it will be used as a quick information card about the project's objectives and activities. The flyer will be uploaded to the project website and shared as printed versions during any future relevant events. The flyer will be updated, if necessary, one more time until the end of the project.

Moreover, one roll-up/poster will be created by month 12 (December 2024), matching the look and feel of the website and the overall project design concept. It will be prepared in English (local languages to be considered if appropriate, or necessary) to raise awareness among the stakeholders and a variety of relevant audiences about the project with succinct textual and graphical information. Printable versions of the roll-up/poster will also be created and provided to partners to be printed and used at the events they participate in.

If necessary, Swarmchestrate will also consider producing event focused posters of smaller size, where the content of the poster will be replaced to fit the needs (theme) of the event. For this reason, the design will be easily adjustable to the requirements individual partners

have, in case an additional or a more specific version is required. The project logo, the EU flag, UKRI logo & pertinent acknowledgements along with the Swarmchestrate website URL and the social media handles must be clearly displayed on all promotional materials.

4.5 Scientific Publications

The dissemination strategy for the Swarmchestrate project encompasses a plan to share research findings and innovations through scholarly communication channels. Key activities within this plan involve the submission of meticulously prepared articles to esteemed peer-reviewed scientific journals, alongside detailed presentations of our findings at influential conference proceedings.

Swarmchestrate partners have set a target of publishing at least 30 peer-reviewed publications *throughout the project duration, plus one year after the project's end*, in journals, conferences, and workshops. Table 4 below presents the relevant publications which will be considered for submission. We expect this list to be further reviewed and populated in the upcoming months as the academic and research partners take a deeper dive in Swarmchestrate results, methodologies, and challenges, which may be relevant for the scientific community.

Table 4 Relevant Publications Considered for Submission

Publication Type	Submission to
Journal Scientific Publication	IEEE Transactions on Cloud Computing
Journal Scientific Publication	IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications
Journal Scientific Publication	Elsevier's Future Generation Computing Systems
Journal Scientific Publication	Springer's Cluster Computing Journal of Networks, Software Tools and Applications
Journal Scientific Publication	Springer's Journal of Cloud Computing
Journal Scientific Publication	Elsevier's Expert Systems with Applications
Conference Scientific Publication	The EuCNC (European Conference on Networks and Communications)
Conference Scientific Publication	IEEE DCOSS-IoT (Distributed Computing in Smart Systems and the Internet of Things)
Conference Scientific Publication	IEEE International Conference on Autonomic Computing and Self-Organising Systems
Conference Scientific Publication	ACM International Conference on Utility and Cloud Computing (UCC)
Conference Scientific Publication	International Conference on Fog and Mobile Edge Computing (FMEC)

Two conference scientific publications have been already published by Swarmchestrate partners at the time of writing this deliverable, acknowledging the project's funding sources. In particular:

- **“FE[r]Chain: Enforcing Fairness in Blockchain Data Exchanges Through Verifiable Functional Encryption”** by C. Foucault, R. Rabbaninejad, T. Dimitriou and A. Michalas. 29th ACM Symposium on Access Control Models and Technologies (SACMAT), 15-17 May 2024
- **“Swarmchestrate: Towards a Fully Decentralised Framework for Orchestrating Applications in the Cloud-to-Edge Continuum”** by T. Kiss, A. Ullah, G. Terstyanszky, O. Kao, S. Becker, Y. Verginadis, A. Michalas, V. Stankovski, A. Kertész, E. Ricci, J. Altmann, B. Egger, F. Tusa, J. Kovács, R. Lovas. Proceedings of the 38th International Conference on Advanced Information Networking and Applications (AINA-2024), Volume 5, 17-19 April 2024

The above-mentioned scientific publications and links to them, as well as all future scientific publications issued by the consortium will be made available through the website of the project, where a specific section has already been created [5].

4.6 Liaisons with Other Projects

An important part of the dissemination activities is the creation and fostering of connections with other projects and initiatives in domains relevant to Swarmchestrate. Through these connections, Swarmchestrate will promote stakeholders clustering, focus on targeted engagement and perform cross-project dissemination activities. The aim is to disseminate project’s outcomes, ensure exchange of knowledge and best practices to the mutual benefit of all parties involved, and increase visibility of Swarmchestrate in the market and potential future clients for its solutions. Therefore, Swarmchestrate will seek developing liaisons and collaborations with:

- DATA-01-04 call projects and similar Horizon Europe projects coming from previous and future calls;
- industrial associations; and
- appropriate standardisation bodies and working groups.

Swarmchestrate plans to nurture at least three liaisons with other projects, co-organise at least two workshops and at least four webinars on common areas. Thanks to the participation of partners in several ongoing projects, associations and initiatives, targeted liaisons and synergies have been already created in order to ensure the broad outreach of the project’s results, fostering effective Swarmchestrate uptake and validation of the project’s platform.

Project Scientific Coordinator Tamas Kiss will discuss the latest advancements and challenges in dynamically connecting edge-cloud resources and the future of the edge-cloud continuum during Madeira Digital Transformation Summit [6]. The panel session will take place on June 26 and Swarmchestrate will be presented along with funded projects from the CL4-2023-DATA-01-04 call, in particular ENACT [7], INTEND [8] and EMPYREAN [9].

Figure 15 Panel Session in Madeira Digital Transformation Summit

At the time of writing this deliverable, a joint webinar is being organised during the first week of October 2024, among all funded projects from the CL4-2023-DATA-01-04 call.

This list will further grow with the addition of relevant organisations and peers that will be identified during the project's lifetime.

4.7 General Media

Engaging with the press media stands as a critical pillar for enhancing visibility and conveying the key project achievements and innovations to a broader audience. This section outlines the approach for establishing and nurturing productive relationships with media outlets across multiple formats, encompassing television, newspapers, radio, and online platforms. The focus extends beyond local reach, aiming for significant presence at both EU and international levels, catering to general as well as specialized media outlets that align with the project's objectives.

To streamline interactions with the media and ensure consistent, coherent communication of Swarmchestrate vision and achievements, a comprehensive press kit will be developed. This kit is envisioned as a key tool for media engagement, equipped with essential resources and materials that accurately represent the project. Components of the **press kit** will include:

- visual identity, ensuring immediate recognition and professional presentation across media channels;

- press releases, ready-to-publish documents that highlight the project's objectives, recent achievements, and upcoming milestones;
- an overarching high-level project presentation (pitch deck), offering a glimpse into the project's background, goals, and the potential impact;
- key messages that convey the core values and highlights of the project; and
- a curated collection of high-quality images that are free from copyright restrictions, allowing for easy use by the press.

The press kit will be made readily available to all project partners, empowering them to establish connections with media outlets and effectively communicate the Swarmchestr^{ate} project's narrative.

Press releases will be published on a regular basis (approximately nine press releases by the end of the project) and coincide with key project achievements (e.g., kick-off meeting, organisation of a large event, implementation of key activities within the project, etc.) and in order to present the results achieved through the Swarmchestr^{ate} demonstrators. All partners will be responsible for engaging with their local media outlets to ensure a wider reach of the press releases. All press releases will be published in a dedicated section on the project's website [10].

4.8 Workshops, Webinars & Training

The organisation of events in the form of workshops, webinars, training sessions and demos will play a crucial role throughout the duration of the project. The consortium plans to organise **two scientific workshops** and several sessions, such as panels, training sessions and demos, throughout the duration of the project. There will be an emphasis on organising face-to-face events but also depending on the feasibility of the conditions, it will be decided whether to organise a remote event.

The dissemination plan includes the organisation of **four short webinars**. The organisation of these webinars will be led by the D&C Leader; the curation of their content, programme and participations will be managed by the Technical Coordinator of the project and the academic partners of the consortium; and the foreseen time schedule for their realisation is one webinar by month 12 on the project concept, one webinar by month 18, and two webinars after releasing all components. Each of these will have a different scientific focus and will be targeted to the edge and fog computing scientific research and industrial communities.

Furthermore, **training and engagement sessions** will be organised, primarily by the academic partners of the consortium, to interact with the general public (e.g., non-scientists, university students, secondary schools, etc.) and inform them about the effect of the project's results in their everyday life, creating awareness on facts regarding the societal benefits for empowering the fog and edge computing and IoT. The goal is to mitigate the gap that typically separates practitioners and theoreticians by providing a series of regular structured training events on topics relevant to the project.

The pertinent organising partners will work with the Dissemination and Communication Leader as well as with the Project Coordinator to further define their plans and begin their preparations for the workshop. These include: main topic(s) definition; key participants and target audiences; scientific program and workshop agenda; promotional material and communication channels, time schedule, logistics and practical issues setup; documentation and reporting.

4.9 Events

Awareness, interaction and promotion regarding Swarmchestrate is expected to be impacted positively by the project representation in relevant events. Events are an important means for the consortium to communicate and disseminate the aims, developments and results of its work. Events are often the only way of interesting mainstream press in EU affairs, to ensure a Press Release and organise interview opportunities with high-profile participants. The project will be supported by the relevant communication material produced, namely the press kit (see section 4.7).

Dedicated and active participation in conferences and workshops co-located with major events to engage with relevant initiatives and other projects in the same call and in the same domains will be an emphasis. Precise timing of these events will be decided during the course of the project, but sufficiently in advance to allow in-depth preparation. Swarmchestrate maintains an internal events overview where upcoming important events are catalogued and will include events organised by IEEE, WIC, ACM, ICPS, 5G networking conferences, etc.

A dedicated page has been already created in the project website [11] to upload announcements and information on upcoming events, as well as news on our participation in and relevant audio-visual material (e.g., photos, videos) from such events. Similarly, the social media accounts of the project will be animated before and during such events where Swarmchestrate contributes to.

4.10 Videos

Recognising the impact of multimedia in engaging online audiences, the Swarmchestrate project will produce 5 short, informative videos. The first video is scheduled for around M12 in the first year, will present the project concept and goals. The following three videos will focus on presenting the use case-related outcomes, and the final video will concentrate on the final outcomes of the project. These videos will be uploaded to the YouTube channel and the LinkedIn page, expected to capture higher engagement rates on social media platforms compared to traditional text or image posts.

4.11 Contributions to Standardisation and Open Source Communities

Reaching the standardisation and open source communities is crucial to innovation within the European Union: in order for the Swarmchestrate project to have a real impact on further research endeavours, and to help the standardisation path, it is essential to reach and gain the interest of these communities.

There are many channels through which the research community can be reached and results of the project can be made available. First of all, it is necessary to publish in open access. Swarmchestrate will provide open access to all publications, using an open source platform (like Zenodo); additionally all publications will be made accessible on the project website, where they will be linked to their DOIs.

Furthermore, the consortium will actively monitor the advancements in relevant standardisation bodies and international associations and disseminate Swarmchestrate's results whenever possible (e.g., AI, Data and Robotics Association (ADRA), International Data Spaces Association (IDSA), Big Data Value Association (BDVA), GAIA-X, etc.)

CONTRIBUTION TO STANDARDISATION ACTIVITIES

TOSCA - Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications

One of the key features of the proposed Swarmchestrate decentralised framework is the TOSCA-based application and resource description template. Application requirements, including application topology, resource requirements and quality of service parameters (e.g., response time, security requirements, energy consumption), and also resource characteristics and capabilities, are described in standardised TOSCA-based documents. UOW has been a long-term contributor of the TOSCA community and since 2020 it is a member of the OASIS Technical Committee that works on the standardisation of TOSCA.

In this role, UOW plans to continuously update the OASIS TOSCA Technical Committee regarding the work in Swarmchestrate and share its experiences when using TOSCA in the decentralised context and the cloud-to-edge continuum. Additionally, Swarmchestrate plans to utilise the new, not yet officially released TOSCA 2.0 specification and be fully compliant with that. The project will feed back its experiences to the technical committee and as such it will influence the evolution of the standard specification.

TUB, and ENU as well as other partners, will raise possible enhancements for the TOSCA technical committee to consider in order to provide more comprehensive applications descriptions as well as resource attributes.

5. Activities Schedule

Table 5 presents a generic timeline that outlines the schedule for executing the various dissemination and communication activities that have been planned. This overview provides insight into the specific timing and sequence of these key initiatives, ensuring a structured approach to engaging with our target audiences and stakeholders.

Table 5 Communication and Dissemination timeline

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36		
Project Website																																						
Social Media																																						
Newsletter																																						
Promo Materials																																						
Scientific Publications																																						
Liaisons w/ other projects																																						
General Media																																						
Conferences, Workshops, Webinars																																						
Videos																																						

EDITORIAL CALENDAR

An editorial calendar has been set-up internally by the project consortium, with at least one social media post per week, at least one blog post per month, and on-demand YouTube video uploads. The editorial calendar has been adjusted to take into account the major holidays around the year (Catholic & Orthodox Easter, Christmas, mid-July to mid-August annual leave).

6. Dissemination and Communication Monitoring

In order to assess the impact of Swarmchestr^{ate} D&C activities, we measure various quantitative figures, as well as the impact of promotional efforts on the attitude of the receivers of the communications messages. This will be feasible through a five-step measurement cycle model, spanning from objective identification to data driven optimisation, which has been put into practice already at the time of composing the project's DoA [12] and is further elaborated in the deliverable at hand:

- Identify the core dissemination and communication objectives (e.g. raise awareness, increase engagement – i.e. acquire more contacts, acquire more participants for our events).
- Set goals for our promotional tactics. We concentrate on how to accomplish our objectives (e.g. inform visitors through the content of our website, intensify events promotion, etc.).
- Identify the project's Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) – the metrics that play a crucial role to the success of the aforementioned utilised tactics and set the expected achievable targets.
- Measure the progress and impact of the conducted activities based on these metrics on a regular basis (i.e., at month 18, at month 36, one year after the project's end). Such metrics will allow the consortium to have a consistent view of the amount and the effectiveness of the conducted D&C activities.
- Adjust and optimise the dissemination strategy towards achieving the expected outcomes and maximising visibility.

Figure 16 Five-step measurement cycle model

Table 6 below presents the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and the achievable targets set for each type of the D&C activities. These KPIs have been defined at the very beginning of the project, aimed at better monitoring the dissemination and communication results across online and offline channels.

Table 6 Swarmchestrate D&C KPIs

Swarmchestrate KPIs Monitoring			
KPIs as per the DoA		Target	Timeframe
Scientific publications/papers and presentations in conferences	Nr of scientific publications submitted	>30	Throughout the project duration +1 year after project's end
Scientific workshops at large conferences	Nr of workshops Nr of attendees	2 >100	Throughout the project duration +1 year after project's end
Short webinars	Nr of webinars	>4	1 by M12 on concept, 1 by M18, 2 after releasing all components
Appearances in general media (News sites, TV, Newspapers)	Nr of appearances	>15	Close to M18 on the overall concept and close to M36 on the outcome presentation
Contributions to SDOs and open source communities	Nr of contributions submitted	>2	After M18 and more active towards end of the project
Liaisons with other projects	Nr of synergies/liaisons	>3	Planning M06; Connection before M12; Actions throughout Y2 and Y3
Co-organised workshops with other projects	Nr of workshops	2	Planning M06; Connection before M12; Actions throughout Y2 and Y3
Co-organised webinars with other projects on common areas	Nr of webinars	4	Planning M06; Connection before M12; Actions throughout Y2 and Y3

Swarmchestrator KPIs Monitoring			
KPIs as per the DoA		Target	Timeframe
Social media followers	Nr of Twitter followers Nr of LinkedIn followers	>500 >500	By end of project
Press releases distributed to media	Nr of press releases	9	press releases after kick-off meeting, by M06, by M24 and by M36
Public appearances	Nr of public appearances	>6	Throughout project duration
Videos available in YouTube and LinkedIn	Nr of videos	5 (1 on the concept, 1 on final outcomes and 3 related to use cases outcomes)	Throughout project duration
Technical brochures/flyers	Nr of brochures/flyers	4	Throughout project duration
Newsletters	Nr of newsletters issued	15 (1st version in M06 and new issues every 3 months to the end of the project)	Throughout project duration
Public events at universities/ colleges and events organised by public authorities	Nr of public events Nr of attendees	>8 >100	Project Y2 & Y3

7. Preliminary Exploitation Considerations

7.1 Preliminary Individual Exploitation Planning

We have collected the preliminary exploitation intentions of the consortium partners at month 6 of the project. Given the fact it is an RIA project, there are many academic partners in the consortium, and we are too early in the project lifecycle, the individual exploitation plans presented in this section are considered preliminary.

Table 7 Swarmchestrate partners preliminary exploitation intentions

Partner Name	Individual Exploitation Plan
SZTAKI	SZTAKI, as an academic organisation, will not directly pursue the commercialisation of its research findings. All intellectual properties developed by SZTAKI will be open access to ensure that these results are freely available to the public.
TUB	TUB, as an academic organisation, does not seek commercial opportunities for its research findings. Instead, all intellectual properties generated, particularly in the areas of logical proximity and matchmaking algorithm studies, will be shared openly. This open-access approach ensures that the knowledge and innovations developed at TUB are freely available to the public, fostering collaboration and further advancements in these fields.
ICCS	ICCS is a non-profit, private law body associated with the School of Electrical and Computer Engineering of the National Technical University of Athens. ICCS was established in 1989 by the Ministry of Education of Greece in order to promote research and development activity in all diverse aspects of computer and telecommunications systems and their applications. The Information Management Unit of ICCS participates in Swarmchestr ate . As an academic institution, ICCS it is not going to pursue the financial exploitation of the research findings. Its research outcome and the intellectual property produced in this project will be available to public through open-access publications and open source code repositories in order to promote knowledge dissemination and the advancement of science and research. ICCS intends to exploit academic publication opportunities to disseminate its core work in terms of the Swarmchestr ate project. Furthermore, ICCS intends to provide insights of the Swarmchestr ate innovations to enterprises and SMEs while participating in training activities regarding the project. ICCS can organise seminars and workshops in organisations which will aim at educating them on how to take advantage of the innovative technologies to enhance modern organisations with valuable application deployments over the computing continuum.
TAU	TAU aims to exploit its academic resources and research outcomes by publishing and presenting research in well-known conferences in the fields of applied cryptography, security, and privacy. Additionally, TAU will cooperate with industry to introduce the project's results to key industry players and the

Partner Name	Individual Exploitation Plan
	large number of startups hosted in the university. This will bring in a large number of master students that will have the opportunity to work on project-related activities as part of their thesis and get a firsthand experience of how research and collaboration in large EU projects is done.
IRI UL	IRI UL (Institute for Innovation and Development of University of Ljubljana) was established jointly by the University of Ljubljana and several technologically advanced Slovenian companies as the intermediary organisation, operating as a service for knowledge and technology transfer of Slovenia's most prominent University. It is a non-profit research institute that actively co-designs, creates and disseminates technological and societal solutions tailored to people and the environment. In partnership with UL, the IRI UL is dedicated to nurturing an open source ecosystem for its research and development results. Furthermore, IRI UL will offer technical support for the upkeep and progress of products via commercial consulting and contractual research services.
UL	The University of Ljubljana is committed to fostering an open source environment for its academic outputs. In pursuit of this, the university will proactively engage with commercial entities, seeking partnerships beyond the consortium to aid in the commercialisation process. Furthermore, the University of Ljubljana will provide technical assistance for product maintenance and advancement through commercial consultancy and contract research arrangements. This approach ensures that the university's innovations are both accessible and supported by robust commercial strategies.
FUELICS	Fuelics is a deep tech manufacturing company with a vertical production facility for industrialisation of smart edge computing battery operated devices. Swarmchestr ate , if it meets its milestones, will offer Fuelics know-how on a new way of decentralised management of our sensors. So, upon a successful execution, Fuelics would like to incorporate or commonly (with other parties) agree on a shared or licenced IP. Likewise, if any of the tools or system Fuelics develops and can be commercialised, we would pursue collaboration among interested partners.
SUITE5	Suite5 Data Intelligence Solutions (S5) expects to acquire further technological and innovation know-how related to smart IoT services and the orchestration of decentralised applications, to further expand its unique solution portfolio on analytics and smart scheduling solutions. S5 aims to experiment on and implement distributed intelligence techniques for (a) matchmaking between applications and resources, and (b) self-organised Swarms, which in turn shall further expand the capabilities of the S5 Enterprise Analytics software. The exploitation of the results and of the work performed inside the Swarmchestr ate project shall help gain insights into novel business models including IoT services in the domains of smart manufacturing, utilities, and energy sectors, where S5 is active and aspires to upgrade its services portfolio.

Partner Name	Individual Exploitation Plan
FEA	The improved DISSECT-CF-Fog simulation tool, maintained by researchers from FEA, represents academic relevance. The improvements make the simulator a valuable tool for future research activities beyond the project's scope, and also enables further possible collaborations with domestic and international partners.
FBK	<p>Being a research centre, FBK will exploit the results, as well as knowledge matured in Swarmchestrate as an opportunity for scientific dissemination through international journals, transactions and conferences and preprints in online repositories (e.g., arXiv, Zenodo), for production of academic material (PhD program courses, courses thought by FBK personnel involved in the project), seminars and tutorials, but also thesis assignments and internships, for technology transfer to industrial third parties. In particular, FBK is associated with HIT (Trentino Innovation Hub), whose mission is to connect research and market innovation demand. Trentinosviluppo is also a partner of HIT (Trentino Innovation Hub), thus connecting directly FBK with local companies, in particular SMEs and start-ups. FBK also pays particular attention to its stakeholders – public administration, private companies and European agencies – by coordinating its global strategy in strong synergy between the two pillars on which the Foundation is based: scientific excellence and impact on the market and society.</p> <p>With this in mind, FBK implements two main actions aimed at directing and coordinating research, development and innovation activities:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> (1) a marketing strategy whose objective is to identify the “reference market”, i.e., what meets the needs and interests of FBK's stakeholders, and FBK's “market products”, i.e., the solutions, products, and services that arise from the needs of stakeholders. (2) business development, whose goal is to define, suggest, and implement a planning strategy, projects and activities that seize the opportunities of the reference market identified by strategic marketing, considering the resources, the skills present (but also those that can be created) at FBK.
UST	UST will commercialise its skills and services as implementers of IoT technology in challenging environments such as those exposed to the weather. The technology developed in Swarmchestrate will allow more efficient and robust implementations and will provide a flagship reference. Additionally, the ability to simulate the site based on sustainability-related data will allow additional services and offerings in rehabilitation of natural spaces.
SNU	SNU is an academic organisation, which does not seek direct commercial exploitation of research results. Any intellectual properties created in the area of optimisation will be shared through publications and lectures. This approach allows for fast knowledge dissemination, fosters further innovations, and enhances collaboration with other creative entities.
ENU	As an academic institution, ENU will not directly seek the commercialisation of the research results. All outputs developed by ENU will be open source on the less restrictive license possible. Furthermore, research results created in the area of orchestration will be shared through publications and lectures. ENU

Partner Name	Individual Exploitation Plan
	will actively search for commercial partners, both inside and outside the consortium, to support the commercialisation of the outputs. ENU will offer technical support for the maintenance and further development of the products based on commercial consultancy/contract research agreements.
UOW	As an academic institution, UOW will not directly pursue the commercialisation of the results. All outputs developed by UOW will be open source on the less restrictive license possible (currently all UOW outputs are licensed under Apache 2). UOW will actively search for commercial partners, both inside and outside the consortium, to support the commercialisation of the outputs. UOW will offer technical support for the maintenance and further development of the products based on commercial consultancy/contract research agreements.

7.2 Identification of Preliminary Project Exploitable Results

At month 6 of the project, a first exercise was conducted to identify the Intellectual Property Rights within Swarmchestrate project. Each partner was tasked to identify the background (BG) and foreground (FG) IPR's related to their contributions to the project and to their work inside the project.

Background IPR's is information held by beneficiaries, owned or controlled by project partners and brought to the project; it may originate from existing knowledge as well as copyright or other type of IPR. According to the CA, Background is defined as "data, know-how or information (...) that is needed to implement the action or exploit the results".

Table 8 Consortium Partners Background IPR's

Background Name	Owner Partner	Short Description of Background	TRL M01 -> TRL M36	Type of Protection (Patent, Copyright, Trade Mark, Utility model, Open source, ...)	How will it be utilised within the Project?	Conditions for Use within the Project (Free to use, Licence fee, Restrictions, NDA, ...)	Conditions for Use outside the Project (Is it confidential? Can it be shared with externals? Is it currently shared with externals? If yes, on what conditions?)
DISSECT-CF-Fog	FEA	The DISSECT-CF-Fog simulator ensures an important background knowledge for the project, since the simulator, with its existing capabilities, provides the framework for implementing the project's solution and serves as the first testbed to measure its efficiency.	3 -> 5	Open source	Supporting decisions by modelling the project's solution	Free to use within the project	Can be shared under the project license (GPL 3.0)

Background Name	Owner Partner	Short Description of Background	TRL M01 -> TRL M36	Type of Protection (Patent, Copyright, Trade Mark, Utility model, Open source, ...)	How will it be utilised within the Project?	Conditions for Use within the Project (Free to use, Licence fee, Restrictions, NDA, ...)	Conditions for Use outside the Project (Is it confidential? Can it be shared with externals? Is it currently shared with externals? If yes, on what conditions?)
MiCADO Cloud Orchestrator	UOW	<p>MiCADO is an open source (Apache 2.0 license), cloud-to-edge orchestration tool. It is available at https://micado-scale.eu/.</p> <p>MiCADO will be used as the starting point for the Swarmchestrate decentralised orchestrator.</p>	7 -> 7 ¹	Apache 2.0 Open Source	It will be used as starting point when designing and developing the Swarmchestrate decentralised orchestrator	Free to use within the project	Subject of licencing agreement
VideoAnony, AudioAnony	FBK	<p>Video and voice anonymisation:</p> <p>1) AudioAnony de-identifies the speaker on the fly using a small board connected to the microphones, therefore anonymising audio signals</p>	<p>VideoAnony: 5 -> 7 (if used)</p> <p>AudioAnony: 6 -> 7</p>	MIT Open source	In support of edge processing in demonstrator (if necessary)	Free to use within the project	Subject of licencing agreement

¹ Micado will not be directly developed in Swarmchestrate, only used as the basis for the new developments.

Background Name	Owner Partner	Short Description of Background	TRL M01 -> TRL M36	Type of Protection (Patent, Copyright, Trade Mark, Utility model, Open source, ...)	How will it be utilised within the Project?	Conditions for Use within the Project (Free to use, Licence fee, Restrictions, NDA, ...)	Conditions for Use outside the Project (Is it confidential? Can it be shared with externals? Is it currently shared with externals? If yes, on what conditions?)
		<p>at the source in a transparent way.</p> <p>2) VideoAnony detects the human faces and car plates and apply blurring to the detected regions to anonymise the identity of human and cars, captured by cameras in public spaces.</p>					
SED@edge: Sound event detection on the very edge	FBK	SED@Edge performs real time analysis of audio streams detecting sound events of interest. It identifies, categorises, and promptly notifies about audio events such as gunshots, people or pet presence, possibly screams, car accidents, etc.	5 -> 7 (if used)	Apache 2.0 Open source	In support of edge processing in demonstrator (if necessary)	Free to use within the project	Subject of licencing agreement

Background Name	Owner Partner	Short Description of Background	TRL M01 -> TRL M36	Type of Protection (Patent, Copyright, Trade Mark, Utility model, Open source, ...)	How will it be utilised within the Project?	Conditions for Use within the Project (Free to use, Licence fee, Restrictions, NDA, ...)	Conditions for Use outside the Project (Is it confidential? Can it be shared with externals? Is it currently shared with externals? If yes, on what conditions?)
Early-exit transformer architectures	FBK	Early-exit architectures introduce exit branches in intermediate stages of the backbone so that the inference time and computational cost can be adjusted to the operational conditions and the available computational budget. Therefore, they can be used to dynamically adjust the network size while minimising the impact on the performance. We have deployed this solution for speech recognition.	5 -> 7 (if used)	Apache 2.0 Open source	In support of edge processing in demonstrator (if necessary)	Free to use within the project	Subject of licencing agreement
Federated learning for heterogeneous models	FBK	Federated learning using early-exit architecture for heterogeneous devices	4 -> 6 (if used)	Apache 2.0 Open source	In support of edge/fog training (if necessary)	Free to use within the project	Subject of licencing agreement

Background Name	Owner Partner	Short Description of Background	TRL M01 -> TRL M36	Type of Protection (Patent, Copyright, Trade Mark, Utility model, Open source, ...)	How will it be utilised within the Project?	Conditions for Use within the Project (Free to use, Licence fee, Restrictions, NDA, ...)	Conditions for Use outside the Project (Is it confidential? Can it be shared with externals? Is it currently shared with externals? If yes, on what conditions?)
IoT Platform	FUELICS	Fuelics has developed a cloud agnostic IoT infrastructure to monitor edge computing sensors that commercially offers to clients. Remote monitoring is centrally orchestrated. Decentralised management is not a feature, and we expect Swarmchestrate to introduce it to our platform.	9 (centralised) 4 -> 6 (decentralised, based on Swarmchestrate)	Industrial secrets	Fuelics IoT platform will be used to implement decentralised management in Smart City sensors for two of the four simulators plus providing a interface (desktop or mobile) for actual monitoring of sensors.	Free to use within the project and up to its termination	Centralised IoT Platform (current Fuelics offering) is offered with a SaaS model. Decentralised management exploiting Swarmchestrate's outcome will be offered with a SaaS model with a shared revenue model for more than one contributor.
Trustworthy management of Decentralized identifiers	UL	The University of Ljubljana (UL) has developed a prototype for Decentralised Identifiers (DIDs) management service. This innovative prototype is designed to be interoperable across various sectors, enhancing the reliability and trustworthiness of digital identification. Presently, it is undergoing testing	2 -> 5 (if used)	Open source	Management of DIDs	Free to use within the project	Subject of licencing agreement

Background Name	Owner Partner	Short Description of Background	TRL M01 -> TRL M36	Type of Protection (Patent, Copyright, Trade Mark, Utility model, Open source, ...)	How will it be utilised within the Project?	Conditions for Use within the Project (Free to use, Licence fee, Restrictions, NDA, ...)	Conditions for Use outside the Project (Is it confidential? Can it be shared with externals? Is it currently shared with externals? If yes, on what conditions?)
		within the domains of education, construction and the pharmaceutical industry, showcasing its potential to revolutionise identity management.					
Event Management System (EMS) of Morphemic/ NebulOuS projects	ICCS	It is a federated monitoring events propagation and processing mechanism that is able to efficiently detect SLOs violations in multi-clouds developed as part of Morphemic RIA project and enhanced with computing continuum support as part of NebulOuS RIA project. EMS is able to deploy, manage and maintain an event processing network that follows the application topology to provide real-time monitoring, propagation and processing of events.	5 -> 7	MPL v2.0 license	It will be used to monitor the microservices deployed by Swarmchestrate and it will trigger any application adaptations that might be required.	Free to use within the project	Free to use MPL v2.0 license

Background Name	Owner Partner	Short Description of Background	TRL M01 -> TRL M36	Type of Protection (Patent, Copyright, Trade Mark, Utility model, Open source, ...)	How will it be utilised within the Project?	Conditions for Use within the Project (Free to use, Licence fee, Restrictions, NDA, ...)	Conditions for Use outside the Project (Is it confidential? Can it be shared with externals? Is it currently shared with externals? If yes, on what conditions?)
Asclepios/ ExtremeXP Data Management	ICCS	As part of ASCLEPIOS RIA project, we introduced AMPLE's Models editor and management system, which focuses on efficient model creation, storage and management towards creating the background knowledge that can be used of context-aware access control in the cloud-to-edge continuum. In addition, we will use as background knowledge the decentralised datasets management system developed as part of the ExtremeXP RIA project.	3 -> 6	Apache 2.0 Open source	It will be used for data storage and management	Free to use within the project	Free to use Apache v2.0 license

Foreground IPR's consists of results, including information, being protectable or not, which are generated under the project; it de-facto belongs to the beneficiary generating it. Can be jointly generated (joint ownership) and can be transferred (third parties).

Table 9 Consortium Partners Foreground IPR's

WP	Project Result (PR) / Achievement	Main Contributing Partner	Further Contributing Partner(s)	Short Description of Foreground	TRL M01 -> TRL M36	Type of Protection (Patent, Copyright, Trade Mark, Utility model, Open source, ...)	Conditions for Use within the Project (Free to use, Licence fee, Restrictions, NDA, ...)	Interest in Further Commercialisation of Project Results (Yes/No)	Conditions for Use after the end of the Project (Free to use, Licence fee, Restrictions, NDA, ...)
WP4	New version of DISSECT-CF-Fog	FEA	SZTAKI, FBK, TUB, UOW	The enhanced DISSECT-CF-Fog simulator, with its novel capabilities for modelling self-organising swarms and the concept of digital twins, is published as an open source tool.	3 -> 5	Free to use	Free to use within the project	No	Open source
WP2	Swarmchestrator decentralised orchestrator	UOW	ENU, SZTAKI	This is the orchestrator component of Swarmchestrator that manages the deployment and run-time management of applications. Whether it can be exploited on its own or only together with the other components (e.g. Swarms management, AI-	1 -> 5	Free to use	Free to use within the project	Yes	Apache 2.0 Open source

WP	Project Result (PR) / Achievement	Main Contributing Partner	Further Contributing Partner(s)	Short Description of Foreground	TRL M01 -> TRL M36	Type of Protection (Patent, Copyright, Trade Mark, Utility model, Open source, ...)	Conditions for Use within the Project (Free to use, Licence fee, Restrictions, NDA, ...)	Interest in Further Commercialisation of Project Results (Yes/No)	Conditions for Use after the end of the Project (Free to use, Licence fee, Restrictions, NDA, ...)
				based optimisation, monitoring system, Knowledge managements System, etc.) remains unknown at this time.					
WP5	Natural environment Digital Twin	UST		Digital Twin of the natural environment - architecture, data and designs.	1 -> 5	Other	Restrictions	Yes	Restrictions
WP1	Logical proximity and swarm formation based on matchmaking	TUB	FBK, UOW	As expressed in detail under WP1 in the proposal text, this unit is to enhance the dimensions of physical proximity and provide more dimensions to the matchmaking algorithms for resource selection for Swarm initialisation.	1 -> 5	Free to use	Free to use within the project	Yes	Open source

WP	Project Result (PR) / Achievement	Main Contributing Partner	Further Contributing Partner(s)	Short Description of Foreground	TRL M01 -> TRL M36	Type of Protection (Patent, Copyright, Trade Mark, Utility model, Open source, ...)	Conditions for Use within the Project (Free to use, Licence fee, Restrictions, NDA, ...)	Interest in Further Commercialisation of Project Results (Yes/No)	Conditions for Use after the end of the Project (Free to use, Licence fee, Restrictions, NDA, ...)
WP2	Decision Support for Energy Optimisation	SNU	UOW, SZTAKI, ENU, ICCS, FUELICS	This component helps resource owners to find an optimum between energy consumption and performance.	2 -> 5	Free to use	Free to use within the project	Yes	Open source
WP5	System Integration	FUELICS	All commercial entities	Transition from centralised to decentralised sensor management will constitute a new feature in Fuelics IoT infrastructure.	2 -> 5	Copyright	Free to use within the project	Yes	Mutual Licence Agreements, Licence fee agreements
WP3	Trustworthy DID management in the computing continuum	UL	ICCS, IRI UL, FEA, UST	Transition to a decentralised DID management service that will incorporate trust attributes that will be defined and used within Swarmchestrat. The DID service will be able to issue credentials to all entities in the computing continuum within Swarmchestrat	2->5 (if used)	Other	Free to use within the project	Yes	Open source

WP	Project Result (PR) / Achievement	Main Contributing Partner	Further Contributing Partner(s)	Short Description of Foreground	TRL M01 -> TRL M36	Type of Protection (Patent, Copyright, Trade Mark, Utility model, Open source, ...)	Conditions for Use within the Project (Free to use, Licence fee, Restrictions, NDA, ...)	Interest in Further Commercialisation of Project Results (Yes/No)	Conditions for Use after the end of the Project (Free to use, Licence fee, Restrictions, NDA, ...)
WP2	Decentralised Event Management System	ICCS	SZTAKI, TUB, SNU, ENU, UOW	This refers to the adaptive, context-aware decentralised monitoring mechanism that will enable self-adaptive adaptations in swarms-based deployments.	5 -> 7	Open source	Free to use within the project	No	Free to use MPL v2.0 license
WP3	Identity and role management system	ICCS	TUNI, UL, IRI UL	It will leverage Decentralized Identifiers (DIDs) to implement a robust identification and authentication mechanism for software agents and resources in the cloud computing continuum. These agents and resources, once registered using Smart Contracts, are considered trusted within the system. DIDs will facilitate the creation and	2 -> 5	Open source	Free to use within the project	No	Free to use MIT license

WP	Project Result (PR) / Achievement	Main Contributing Partner	Further Contributing Partner(s)	Short Description of Foreground	TRL M01 -> TRL M36	Type of Protection (Patent, Copyright, Trade Mark, Utility model, Open source, ...)	Conditions for Use within the Project (Free to use, Licence fee, Restrictions, NDA, ...)	Interest in Further Commercialisation of Project Results (Yes/No)	Conditions for Use after the end of the Project (Free to use, Licence fee, Restrictions, NDA, ...)
				association of identities with various functionalities, ensuring that resources operate only under the conditions where they have the appropriate rights and permissions.					
WP3	Decentralised knowledge base	ICCS	UL, IRI UL, FEA, UST	A dedicated mechanism that will support the decentralised management of data processing across the cloud computing continuum. This mechanism will materialise a decentralised knowledge base that will enable effective decision-making for resource allocation and application reconfiguration	3 -> 6	Open source	Free to use within the project	No	Free to use Apache v2.0 license

Project WP	Main Result (PR) / Achievement	Contributing Partner	Further Contributing Partner(s)	Short Description of Foreground	TRL M01 -> TRL M36	Type of Protection (Patent, Copyright, Trade Mark, Utility model, Open source, ...)	Conditions for Use within the Project (Free to use, Licence fee, Restrictions, NDA, ...)	Interest in Further Commercialisation of Project Results (Yes/No)	Conditions for Use after the end of the Project (Free to use, Licence fee, Restrictions, NDA, ...)
				across the cloud continuum.					

The following preliminary exploitable results have been identified as of month 6 in Swarmchestrator project.

Table 10 Swarmchestrator Preliminary Exploitable Results

ER number	Exploitable Result Name	Short Description of Exploitable Result	Main Partner	Contributing Partner(s)
ER1	DISSECT-CF-Fog	The simulator can be developed into a standalone service, providing a platform for further experimentation and fine-tuning for the Cloud-to-Edge Continuum.	FEA	SZTAKI, FBK, TUB, UOW, ENU
ER2	Decentralised Orchestrator (not final, name has not been decided yet)	This is the orchestrator component of Swarmchestrator that manages the deployment and run-time management of applications. Whether it can be exploited on its own or only together with the other components (e.g. Swarms management, AI-based optimisation, monitoring system, Knowledge managements System, etc.) remains unknown at this time.	UOW	ENU, SZTAKI

ER number	Exploitable Result Name	Short Description of Exploitable Result	Main Partner	Contributing Partner(s)
ER3	Algorithms for logical proximity, swarm formation, and swarm management	Centralised and decentralised algorithms for selecting the resources that form swarms at application launch and modify swarms during application runtime.	FBK	TUB
ER4	Decentralised Device Management as implemented in Demos 1 & 2		FUELICS	FBK, SZTAKI
ER5	Decentralised Event Management System	This refers to the adaptive, context-aware decentralised monitoring mechanism that will enable self-adaptive adaptations in swarms-based deployments. It can be exploited individually.	ICCS	SZTAKI, TUB, SNU, ENU, UOW
ER6	Identity and role management system	It will leverage Decentralized Identifiers (DIDs) to implement a robust identification and authentication mechanism for software agents and resources in the cloud computing continuum. These agents and resources, once registered using Smart Contracts, are considered trusted within the system. DIDs will facilitate the creation and association of identities with various functionalities, ensuring that resources operate only under the conditions where they have the appropriate rights and permissions. It can be exploited individually.	ICCS	TUNI, UL, IRI UL
ER7	Decentralised knowledge base	A dedicated mechanism that will support the decentralized management of data processing across the cloud computing continuum. This mechanism will materialise a decentralized knowledge base that will enable effective decision-making for resource allocation and application reconfiguration across the cloud continuum. It can be exploited individually.	ICCS	UL, IRI UL, FEA, UST

8. Conclusions & Next Steps

Deliverable 6.1 “Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan” has been prepared at M6 of the project; it provides guidelines for the consortium partners to execute and a consistent monitoring methodology to measure and adjust all planned project activities to ensure the broad visibility, adequate promotion, and uptake of results of the Swarmchestrate project.

The document at hand presents the communication, dissemination, and community-building strategy, describes and reports on the various activities conducted between M1 and M6 of the project, outlines the planned promotional activities for the coming months, and touches upon the preliminary exploitation intentions of the consortium partners.

Developing the communication, dissemination and exploitation plan at the early stages of the project will allow Swarmchestrate to start on the right foot with the aforementioned activities and sustain a good momentum throughout the project. Using this plan will help the consortium partners to:

- Execute outreach activities in a unified manner and within the planned schedule;
- Produce messages which are consistent and of a high standard; and ultimately
- Contribute in an effective way to promoting the project.

WP6 is a horizontal Work Package and its activities run in parallel with the design, development, and demonstration tasks of the other WPs. The communication, dissemination and exploitation plan is considered dynamic and should be periodically evaluated and adjusted throughout the project duration to ensure optimal results in impact creation. Upcoming deliverables D6.2 and D7.1 (in the context of WP7, which will kick-off on M19 of the project) will provide details on the progress, achieved KPIs, attended and organized events, and the effectiveness of Swarmchestrate’s online presence at M18 and M36 respectively.

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Annex A – Swarmchestrate Visual Guidelines

Visual Communication

swarmchestrate

- **Logo Font:** Croogla 4F
- **Website Font** (to be used on the website and all promotional material): Overpass (Open-Source, typeface font <https://fonts.google.com/specimen/Overpass>)

Light 300

Whereas recognition of the inherent dignity

Light 300 italic*Whereas recognition of the inherent dignity*

- **Alternative Font** (to be used for presentations and deliverables): Calibri Light (standard pre-installed in modern Windows editions)

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Colour Palette

HEX #162D73
R22 G45 B115HEX #0455BF
R4 G85 B191HEX #D5E2F2
R213 G226 B242HEX #368DD9
R54 G141 B217HEX #94C6F2
R148 G198 B242

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- In all activities: media relations, conferences, seminars,...
- On all information material: website, publications, posters, presentations, roll-ups,...
- In all formats: paper, digital,...
- On all supports: infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major results funded
- EC download center for visual elements (https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/information-sources/logo-download-center_en)

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Templates

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- PowerPoint template available in: [Nextcloud](#)>Work Packages>WP6>Templates
- MS Word template available in: [Nextcloud](#)>Work Packages>WP6>Templates

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Social Media Presence

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Communication Action: Social media

<p>Target values: >500 followers in twitter; >500 followers in LinkedIn</p>	<p>Purpose: Use online social media sites, such as Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook and YouTube, as a two-way access between the project partners and technical and public audiences. The content is updated on a regular basis and the feedback will help to influence the project's direction</p>
<p>Time plan: established at M01; publish announcements and initiate discussions from M06.</p>	

- Social Media Tagging Sheet (Nextcloud>Work Packages>WP6)
 - Add the social media & website of your organization
 - Add the social media of key persons (not mandatory)
 - Add external accounts/ organizations to follow
 - Add contacts for dissemination
- Contribute to gaining followers on our social media – our shared responsibility
- Like/follow and share among your co-workers, partners, etc.
- On social media always
 - Repost our project's posts
 - Tag @swarmchestrate – this is mandatory
- Hashtags: #SwarmchestrateEU; #orchestration; #swarm; #EnergyEfficiency; #edge_computing; #fog_computing; #IoT

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